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Adaptive Observer-Based Line-of-Sight Guidance Law for Path Following of Underactuated Unmanned Surface Vehicle with Sideslip Compensation

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ABSTRACT In this paper, the path following problem of an underactuated unmanned surface vehicle (USV) in the presence of environmental disturbances is considered. To compensate for the sideslip induced by drift forces, an adaptive Kalman-like observer is proposed to estimate both the path following errors and the unknown sideslip angle. Based on the estimated angle, an adaptive observer-based line-of-sight (AO-LOS) guidance law is then constructed to ensure convergence to the desired path. It has been proven that the proposed sideslip estimator is uniformly globally exponentially stable (UGES), while the equilibrium of the cascade system, composed of the sideslip estimator and guidance law, is shown to be uniformly semiglobally exponentially stable (USGES). Several numerical and experimental examples are provided to validate the theoretical results and demonstrate the practical applicability of the AO-LOS guidance law.

INDEX TERMS Adaptive observer, line-of-sight, LOS, path following, sideslip estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

OVER the last decade, unmanned surface vehicles (USVs) have garnered increased research interest due to their significant potential for diverse marine applications, including civilian harbor protection, environmental sampling and monitoring, search and rescue operations, and resource exploration [1]–[4]. A USV relies on the proper design of a guidance system to accomplish a variety of motion control scenarios, including path following [5], path maneuvering [6], path tracking [7], and target tracking [8]. In the path following problem, the control objective is to develop a kinematic guidance law such that the vehicle moves along a desired geometric path, without temporal specifications. To achieve this goal, different kinds of guidance laws have been proposed and analyzed in the literature [9]–[12].

The line-of-sight (LOS) is a cost-effective and commonly employed guidance strategy that ensures convergence to the desired path by mimicking the heading angle command of an experienced sailor [9]. However, the conventional LOS method may lead to misguidance if the vehicle is exposed

to the unknown drift forces caused by environmental disturbances such as ocean currents, wind, and waves. These forces, in particular, influence the actual direction of a USV's motion, resulting in a deviation from its heading direction, which is referred to as a sideslip. It has been shown that even a small sideslip angle may cause significant path following errors [9]. The sideslip angle can be measured using optical correlation sensors or calculated from surge and sway speed measurements, and then directly compensated in the guidance law. However, the first approach is expensive to implement, while the second approach is prone to errors due to measurement noise and bias [9].

In [13], the integral LOS (ILOS) guidance law was introduced to compensate for the influence of unknown ocean currents during straight-line following by incorporating an integral term within the classical LOS guidance law. This method was extended to curved paths in [14] and thoroughly analyzed in [15], where the authors demonstrated that the equilibrium of the closed-loop guidance system is uniformly locally exponentially stable (ULES) and uniformly globally

asymptotically stable (UGAS), or equivalently, globally κ -exponentially stable. Another approach, known as the adaptive LOS (ALOS) [16], [17], treats the sideslip angle as an unknown parameter to be estimated. The closed-loop system under the ALOS guidance law has been proven to be uniformly semi-globally exponentially stable (USGES), which ensures stronger convergence and robustness properties compared to global κ -exponential stability. According to [17], ALOS performs comparably to ILOS when the sideslip angle is nearly constant but outperforms it in compensating for rapidly varying sideslip angles caused by time-varying disturbances. However, to avoid large oscillations during the transient, the adaptation gain in the ALOS cannot be set too high, which limits its convergence speed. Several methods with a time-varying look-ahead distance have been proposed to enhance the performance of classical ILOS and ALOS [18], [19].

To overcome the limitations of ILOS and ALOS-based guidance methods, numerous observer-based guidance laws have been proposed in the literature [20], [21]. In [22], the authors introduced an extended state observer-based LOS (ELOS) guidance law capable of fast sideslip estimation without oscillations. However, the ELOS method mitigates oscillations at the cost of degrading the USGES to the input-to-state stability (ISS) property [17], [22]. Furthermore, in practice, the convergence speed of ELOS can be constrained by its sensitivity to measurement noise [22]. An improved ELOS guidance algorithm with an adaptive look-ahead distance that depends on cruising speed and cross-tracking error is developed in [23]. Alternatively, the predictor-based LOS (PLOS) method uses a USV model to predict cross-track and along-track errors, which are then employed to estimate the sideslip angle [24], [25]. However, while PLOS can provide a fast and smooth estimate, its performance may be significantly degraded by variations in USV velocity. In [24], it is proven that the PLOS-based guidance system is UGAS, which is a weaker stability property than USGES. Recently, a predictor-based method that combines the advantages of PLOS and ILOS has been proposed in [26].

In this paper, we propose a novel adaptive observer-based LOS path following guidance law, referred to as AO-LOS, which effectively compensates for sideslip induced by drift forces. In the proposed approach, the sideslip angle is treated as an unknown system state and is estimated alongside cross-track and along-track errors using an adaptive Kalman-like observer. It has been proven that the equilibrium point of the estimation subsystem is uniformly globally exponentially stable (UGES), and the equilibrium of the cascade system, comprising the sideslip estimator and guidance law, is uniformly semiglobally exponentially stable (USGES). The proposed guidance law has been validated through extensive numerical simulations and experiments on a real vehicle.

In contrast to existing methods that rely on fixed gains, the proposed approach utilizes adaptive gains for estimating the sideslip angle. This adaptive mechanism ensures uniform global exponential stability of the estimation error dynamics, while other methods are characterized by weaker stabil-

FIGURE 1. Geometric representation of the LOS guidance.

ity properties. Consequently, the proposed method achieves faster sideslip angle estimation with reduced sensitivity to measurement noise. Specifically, the AO-LOS method provides an exponential convergence rate, whereas the ALOS and PLOS exhibit asymptotic convergence and may experience large oscillations. Compared to the ELOS, the AO-LOS is less sensitive to measurement noise, which is crucial for practical applications. Furthermore, due to the UGES property, the AO-LOS guidance law ensures more robust path following performance across various USV speeds and initial conditions compared to other methods, which may exhibit significant performance variations under different operating conditions.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section II, the kinematics model of a USV is introduced and the path following problem is formulated. Section III contains the proposed adaptive observer-based guidance law along with stability analysis. Simulation and experimental results are presented in Section IV, followed by concluding remarks in Section V.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The body-fixed reference frame $\langle b \rangle$ and earth-fixed inertial frame $\langle e \rangle$ are utilized to describe the motion of a USV, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The kinematic model of a three degree-of-freedom motion of a USV is described as follows [27]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x} = u \cos \psi - v \sin \psi \\ \dot{y} = u \sin \psi + v \cos \psi \\ \dot{\psi} = r \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where x , y and ψ denote the position and heading (yaw) angle of a USV in the frame $\langle e \rangle$, while u , v and r represent the surge velocity, sway velocity and yaw rate of a USV in the frame $\langle b \rangle$, respectively.

The reference path \mathcal{P} is parameterized as $(x_d(\theta), y_d(\theta))$, where θ denotes the path scalar variable. Let $\langle p \rangle$ denote the local path-tangential frame with the origin at $(x_d(\theta), y_d(\theta))$. At any point $(x_d(\theta), y_d(\theta))$, the frame $\langle p \rangle$ is rotated by an angle

$$\alpha_d(\theta) = \text{atan2}(y'_d(\theta), x'_d(\theta)),$$

with respect to the frame $\langle e \rangle$, where $x'_d(\theta) = \partial x_d / \partial \theta$ and $y'_d(\theta) = \partial y_d / \partial \theta$.

For a USV located at position (x, y) and the desired position $(x_d(\theta), y_d(\theta))$, the along-track error x_e and cross-track error y_e expressed in the frame $\langle p \rangle$ are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_e \\ y_e \end{bmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\alpha_d(\theta)) & -\sin(\alpha_d(\theta)) \\ \sin(\alpha_d(\theta)) & \cos(\alpha_d(\theta)) \end{bmatrix}^T}_{R(\alpha_d(\theta))} \begin{bmatrix} x - x_d(\theta) \\ y - y_d(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $R(\alpha_d(\theta)) \in SO(2)$ is the rotation matrix from $\langle e \rangle$ to $\langle p \rangle$ frame. Differentiation of (2) along (1) gives the path following error dynamics

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_e = U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) \cos \beta - U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \sin \beta \\ \quad + \dot{\alpha}_d y_e - u_d, \\ \dot{y}_e = U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \cos \beta + U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) \sin \beta \\ \quad - \dot{\alpha}_d x_e. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $U = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$ is the resultant speed of a USV, $\beta = \text{atan2}(v, u)$ is the unknown sideslip angle, whereas u_d represents the speed of the moving reference point defined as

$$u_d = \dot{\theta} \sqrt{x_d'^2(\theta) + y_d'^2(\theta)}. \quad (4)$$

The control objective is to construct the guidance law and path variable update law $\dot{\theta}$ such that a USV follows the desired reference path $(x_d(\theta), y_d(\theta))$, i.e., to achieve $(x_e, y_e) \rightarrow (0, 0)$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$.

In this paper, we make use of the following assumptions.

Assumption 1: The sideslip angle β is small and constant, that is $\dot{\beta} = 0$.

Assumption 2: The autopilot for heading control achieves perfect tracking of the desired heading angle ψ_d , that is $\psi = \psi_d$.

Remark 1: Both Assumptions 1 and 2 are common in the literature [16]–[19], [22]–[26]. Typically, the sideslip angle is less than 5° , yet it can still cause significant deviations from the desired path if not properly compensated for [16]. During straight-line following, the sideslip angle is nearly constant, while it becomes time-varying when following curved paths. However, if the sideslip estimation subsystem is designed with sufficiently high bandwidth, it will be capable of effectively tracking variations in the sideslip angle [22]. Assumption 2 is made to enable the stability analysis of the closed-loop guidance system at the kinematic level, independent of vehicle dynamics. This assumption can be relaxed by considering the design of the heading control system and analyzing the cascade connection between the guidance system and the heading autopilot, as in [28]. In that scenario, the stability analysis would remain similar to that presented in this paper, provided the heading angle tracking error meets certain more realistic conditions.

III. ADAPTIVE OBSERVER-BASED GUIDANCE LAW

In this section, we introduce an adaptive observer for estimating the unknown sideslip angle of a USV. Subsequently, we propose an adaptive observer-based LOS guidance law (AOLOS) that drives USV towards a desired parameterized path. The stability of the resulting guidance system is then proven using the cascade systems stability theory.

A. ADAPTIVE OBSERVER

Assumption 1 implies that $\sin \beta \approx \beta$ and $\cos \beta \approx 1$. Thus, the path following error dynamics (3) can be simplified as [16]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_e = U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) - U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \beta + \dot{\alpha}_d y_e - u_d, \\ \dot{y}_e = U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) + U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) \beta - \dot{\alpha}_d x_e. \end{cases} \quad (5a)$$

$$(5b)$$

In order to construct an observer for sideslip angle estimation, we begin by rewriting the path following error dynamic model (5) in the matrix form:

$$\dot{z} = A(t)z + \varphi(t) + \Phi(t)\beta \quad (6)$$

where $z = [x_e \ y_e]^T$, $\varphi(t) = [U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) - u_d \ U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d)]^T$, $\Phi(t) = [-U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \ U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)]^T$ and $A(t) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \dot{\alpha}_d \\ -\dot{\alpha}_d & 0 \end{bmatrix}$.

Motivated by [29], we propose the following adaptive Kalman-like observer

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\hat{z}} = A(t)\hat{z} + \varphi(t) + \Phi(t)\hat{\beta} + [p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda\Lambda^T + P_z^{-1}]\Sigma(z - \hat{z}), \\ \dot{\hat{\beta}} = p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda^T\Sigma(z - \hat{z}). \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $P_z \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$ and $p_\beta \in \mathbb{R}$ are solution to the following differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\Lambda} = [A(t) - P_z^{-1}\Sigma]\Lambda + \Phi(t), \\ \dot{P}_z = -\rho_z P_z - A(t)^T P_z - P_z A(t) + \Sigma, \quad P_z(t_0) > 0, \\ \dot{p}_\beta = -\rho_\beta p_\beta + \Lambda^T \Sigma \Lambda, \quad p_\beta(t_0) > 0. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Here, $\rho_\beta, \rho_z > 0$ are sufficiently large constants, and Σ is a positive definite matrix.

It is noteworthy that the first equation in (7) is employed to estimate x_e and y_e , while the second equation is utilized to estimate the unknown sideslip angle β . The time evolution of adaptive gains utilized in (7) is governed by (8).

Let $\tilde{z} = \hat{z} - z$ and $\tilde{\beta} = \hat{\beta} - \beta$. Then, (7) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\tilde{z}} = (A(t) - [p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda\Lambda^T + P_z^{-1}]\Sigma)\tilde{z} + \Phi(t)\tilde{\beta}, \\ \dot{\tilde{\beta}} = -p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda^T\Sigma\tilde{z}. \end{cases}$$

Furthermore, the transformation $\tilde{\varepsilon} = \tilde{z} - \Lambda\tilde{\beta}$ yields the following equation

$$\dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}} = (A(t) - [p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda\Lambda^T + P_z^{-1}]\Sigma)\tilde{\varepsilon} + \Phi(t)\tilde{\beta} - \dot{\Lambda}\tilde{\beta} - \Lambda\dot{\tilde{\beta}}.$$

Finally, after substituting expressions for $\dot{\Lambda}$ and $\dot{\tilde{\beta}}$ into the previous equation, we get

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\tilde{\varepsilon}} = (A(t) - P_z^{-1}\Sigma)\tilde{\varepsilon} \\ \dot{\tilde{\beta}} = -p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda^T\Sigma(\tilde{\varepsilon} + \Lambda\tilde{\beta}) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The following two properties, which are standard in the system identification literature [29], need to be satisfied to guarantee the convergence of $\tilde{\varepsilon}$ and $\tilde{\beta}$.

Property 1: (Uniform observability) The pair $(A(t), \Sigma^{\frac{1}{2}})$ is uniformly completely observable, in the sense that there exist $0 < \underline{\gamma}_1 < \overline{\gamma}_1$, $T_1 > 0$ and $t_0 \geq 0$ such that $\forall t \geq t_0$:

$$\underline{\gamma}_1 I \leq \int_t^{t+T_1} \Psi(\tau, t)^T \Sigma \Psi(\tau, t) d\tau \leq \overline{\gamma}_1 I, \quad (10)$$

where Ψ is the transition matrix of the system $\dot{z} = A(t)z$ and $\Sigma > 0$ is bounded.

Property 2: (Persistent excitation condition) The matrix $\Phi(t)$ is such that the vector $\Lambda(t)$, which is driven by $\Phi(t)$ through (8), satisfies

$$\underline{\gamma}_2 I \leq \int_t^{t+T_2} \Lambda(\tau)^T \Sigma \Lambda(\tau) d\tau \leq \bar{\gamma}_2 I, \quad (11)$$

for some $0 < \underline{\gamma}_2 < \bar{\gamma}_2$, $T_2 > 0$, $\Sigma > 0$, $t_0 \geq 0$, and $\forall t \geq t_0$.

It can be easily verified that $\Psi(t) = e^{A(t)t} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \alpha_d & \sin \alpha_d \\ -\sin \alpha_d & \cos \alpha_d \end{bmatrix}$, which is a rotation matrix. Therefore, the matrices $\Psi(t)^T \Sigma \Psi(t)$ and Σ share the same eigenvalues. This implies that condition (10) is satisfied for any bounded $\Sigma > 0$. Furthermore, under the assumption that $A(t) - P_z^{-1} \Sigma$ is stable, the upper bound in condition (11) always exists since $\Phi(t)$ is bounded. On the other hand, the vector $\Lambda(t)$ can be viewed as a filtered version of the vector $\Phi(t) = [-U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \quad U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)]^T$, which is nonzero at each time instant t . Consequently, the scalar $\Lambda(t)^T \Sigma \Lambda(t)$ is positive, ensuring the existence of the lower bound in condition (11) [30].

Lemma 1: The adaptive observer composed of the (7) and (8) renders the origin $(\tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) = (0, 0)$ of the system (9) UGES.

Proof: According to Lemma 2.1 in [31], under the conditions (10) and (11), the solutions $P_z(t)$ and $p_\beta(t)$ of differential equations in (8) are positive definite for all $t > t_0$. Therefore, we can consider the following candidate Lyapunov function

$$V_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) = \tilde{\varepsilon}^T P_z \tilde{\varepsilon} + p_\beta \tilde{\beta}^2.$$

Taking the derivative with respect to time of the function $V_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta})$ and using (8) and (9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) &= -\rho_z \tilde{\varepsilon}^T P_z \tilde{\varepsilon} - \rho_\beta p_\beta \tilde{\beta}^2 - \tilde{\varepsilon}^T \Sigma \tilde{\varepsilon} \\ &\quad - \tilde{\varepsilon}^T \Sigma \Lambda \tilde{\beta} - \tilde{\beta} \Lambda^T \Sigma \tilde{\varepsilon} - \Lambda^T \Sigma \Lambda \tilde{\beta}^2. \end{aligned}$$

Since $-\tilde{\varepsilon}^T \Sigma \tilde{\varepsilon} - \tilde{\varepsilon}^T \Sigma \Lambda \tilde{\beta} - \tilde{\beta} \Lambda^T \Sigma \tilde{\varepsilon} - \Lambda^T \Sigma \Lambda \tilde{\beta}^2 = -(\tilde{\varepsilon} + \Lambda \tilde{\beta})^T \Sigma (\tilde{\varepsilon} + \Lambda \tilde{\beta}) \leq 0$, it follows that

$$\dot{V}_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) \leq -\rho_z \tilde{\varepsilon}^T P_z \tilde{\varepsilon} - \rho_\beta p_\beta \tilde{\beta}^2 \leq -\rho (\tilde{\varepsilon}^T P_z \tilde{\varepsilon} + p_\beta \tilde{\beta}^2),$$

which finally gives $\dot{V}_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) \leq -\rho V_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta})$ for $\rho = \min(\rho_z, \rho_\beta) > 0$.

By applying comparison lemma ([32], Lemma 3.4), for all $t \geq t_0$, we have

$$V_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) \leq e^{-\rho(t-t_0)} V_1(t_0, \tilde{\varepsilon}(t_0), \tilde{\beta}(t_0)).$$

Denote by $\underline{\sigma}$ the minimum of the smallest singular value of the matrix $\text{diag}(P_z(t), p_\beta(t))$ for all $t \geq t_0$, and by $\bar{\sigma}_0$ the largest singular value of the matrix $\text{diag}(P_z(t_0), p_\beta(t_0))$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(t)^T \underline{\sigma} \zeta(t) &\leq V_1(t, \tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) \leq e^{-\rho(t-t_0)} V_1(t_0, \tilde{\varepsilon}(t_0), \tilde{\beta}(t_0)) \\ &\leq e^{-\rho(t-t_0)} \zeta(t_0)^T \bar{\sigma}_0 \zeta(t_0), \end{aligned}$$

where $\zeta = [\tilde{\varepsilon}^T \quad \tilde{\beta}]^T$. Therefore,

$$\underline{\sigma} \|\zeta(t)\|^2 \leq \bar{\sigma}_0 e^{-\rho(t-t_0)} \|\zeta(t_0)\|^2,$$

and

$$\|\zeta(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\sigma}_0}{\underline{\sigma}}} e^{-\frac{\rho}{2}(t-t_0)} \|\zeta(t_0)\|, \quad (12)$$

for all $t \geq t_0$ and any $t_0 \geq 0$, $\zeta(t_0) \in \mathbb{R}^3$. Hence, we can conclude that the equilibrium point $(\tilde{\varepsilon}, \tilde{\beta}) = (0, 0)$ is uniformly globally exponentially stable (UGES) ([33], Definition 2.7). ■

Remark 2: For $\rho_z = \rho_\beta = \rho$, the adaptive observer composed of (7) and (8) is equivalent to the following adaptive observer [29]:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{z}} \\ \dot{\hat{\beta}} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} A(t) & \Phi(t) \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \hat{z} \\ \hat{\beta} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \varphi(t) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + S^{-1} H^T \Sigma (z - \hat{z}), \\ \dot{S} &= -\rho S - F(t)^T S - S F(t)^T + H^T \Sigma H, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $F(t) = \begin{bmatrix} A(t) & \Phi(t) \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $H = \begin{bmatrix} I_2 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$. Note that this observer has a Kalman-like structure and converges exponentially with a tunable rate controlled by the parameter ρ . In practice, setting a higher value for the parameter ρ increases the convergence speed, but it also makes the estimates more sensitive to measurement noise. Therefore, one must carefully compromise between convergence speed and accuracy. Alternatively, one can adopt the Lyapunov equation $\dot{S} = -SQS - F(t)^T S - S F(t)^T + H^T \Sigma H$ instead of the one used in equation (13), where Q represents the classical process covariance matrix [34].

Remark 3: To prevent an undesired transient behavior, \tilde{z} should be initialized to zero, which is feasible since x_e and y_e are measured. Under this condition, $|\hat{\beta}(t)|$ will satisfy $|\hat{\beta}(t)| \leq |\beta| + \sqrt{\frac{\bar{\sigma}_0}{\underline{\sigma}}} e^{-\frac{\rho}{2}(t-t_0)} |\beta|$ when $\hat{\beta}(t_0) = 0$, which directly follows from (12).

Remark 4: The proposed sideslip estimation algorithm is adaptive in the sense that its gains Λ , P_z , and p_β are not constant but are dynamically updated according to equation (8). Lemma 1 demonstrates that with these gains, the estimator (7) is uniformly globally exponentially stable (UGES) as long as the parameters ρ_z and ρ_β are positive and the matrix Σ is positive definite. The UGES property ensures that the sideslip estimation performance remains consistent across various USV speeds and initial conditions. In contrast, other methods rely on fixed gains, which results in weaker stability properties and performance that may vary significantly under different operating conditions.

B. ADAPTIVE OBSERVER-BASED GUIDANCE LAW DESIGN

In this subsection, we introduce the adaptive guidance law with sideslip compensation and analyze its stability properties.

In order to compensate for the sideslip angle, the desired heading angle is designed as:

$$\psi_d = \alpha_d(\theta) - \arctan\left(\frac{1}{\Delta} y_e + \hat{\beta}\right), \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta > 0$ is a look-ahead distance as depicted in Fig. 1. Note that $\alpha_d(\theta)$ is known, y_e is measured and $\hat{\beta}$ is estimated by the observer presented in the previous subsection.

The virtual input u_d in (5a) is chosen as

$$u_d = U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) - U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) \hat{\beta} + k_1 x_e, \quad (15)$$

where $k_1 > 0$ is a constant gain parameter. By taking into account (4), one can obtain the following path variable update law

$$\dot{\theta} = \frac{U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) - U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d)\hat{\beta} + k_1 x_e}{\sqrt{x_d'^2(\theta) + y_d'^2(\theta)}}. \quad (16)$$

By substituting (15) into (5a), the along-track error dynamics takes the form

$$\dot{x}_e = -k_1 x_e + U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta} + \dot{\alpha}_d y_e. \quad (17)$$

Furthermore, from (14) under Assumption 2 it follows that $\psi - \alpha_d(\theta) = -\arctan\left(\frac{1}{\Delta}y_e + \hat{\beta}\right)$. Consequently, the following expressions hold

$$\begin{aligned} \sin(\psi - \alpha_d) &= -\frac{y_e + \Delta\hat{\beta}}{\sqrt{(y_e + \Delta\hat{\beta})^2 + \Delta^2}}, \\ \cos(\psi - \alpha_d) &= \frac{\Delta}{\sqrt{(y_e + \Delta\hat{\beta})^2 + \Delta^2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Substituting (18) in (5b), the cross-track error dynamics can be represented as:

$$\dot{y}_e = -k_2 y_e - U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta} - \dot{\alpha}_d x_e, \quad (19)$$

where $k_2 = \frac{U}{\sqrt{(y_e + \Delta\hat{\beta})^2 + \Delta^2}} > 0$.

Finally, the dynamics of the along-track and cross-track errors can be written as

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_e = -k_1 x_e + U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta} + \dot{\alpha}_d y_e \\ \dot{y}_e = -k_2 y_e - U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta} - \dot{\alpha}_d x_e \end{cases}. \quad (20)$$

Lemma 2: Assume that $\Delta_{\min} < \Delta < \Delta_{\max}$, $U > U_{\min}$, and $|\hat{\beta}(t)| < \hat{\beta}_{\max}$. Then the equilibrium point $(x_e, y_e) = (0, 0)$ of the unforced subsystem in (20) (when $\tilde{\beta} = 0$) is USGES.

Proof: Consider the following Lyapunov function

$$V_2(t, x_e, y_e) = \frac{1}{2}(x_e^2 + y_e^2).$$

The time-derivative $\dot{V}_2(t, x_e, y_e)$ along the trajectories (20) for $\tilde{\beta} = 0$ is:

$$\dot{V}_2(t, x_e, y_e) = -k_1 x_e^2 - k_2 y_e^2. \quad (21)$$

Since $V_2(t, x_e, y_e) > 0$ for all $(x_e, y_e) \neq 0$, and $\dot{V}_2(t, x_e, y_e) \leq 0$, it follows that the origin $(x_e, y_e) = (0, 0)$ is uniformly stable. Moreover, $V_2(t, x_e, y_e) \leq 0$ implies that $V_2(t, x_e(t), y_e(t)) \leq V_2(t_0, x_e(t_0), y_e(t_0))$, i.e.:

$$x_e^2(t) + y_e^2(t) \leq x_e^2(t_0) + y_e^2(t_0), \quad \forall t \geq t_0.$$

Furthermore, for each $\gamma > 0$ and all $\sqrt{x_e^2(t) + y_e^2(t)} < \gamma$, the following inequality holds

$$k_1 + k_2 \geq 2 \min\left(k_1, \frac{U_{\min}}{\sqrt{(\gamma + \Delta_{\max}\hat{\beta}_{\max})^2 + \Delta_{\max}^2}}\right) = \mu^*(\gamma).$$

Consequently,

$$\dot{V}_2(t, x_e, y_e) \leq -\mu^*(\gamma)(x_e^2 + y_e^2) \leq -2\mu^*(\gamma)V_2(t, x_e, y_e). \quad (22)$$

Since the origin is uniformly stable, the equality (22) is valid for all trajectories generated by the initial conditions satisfying $\sqrt{x_e^2(t_0) + y_e^2(t_0)} < \gamma$.

FIGURE 2. Modular interconnection of two subsystems.

Employing the comparison lemma yields

$$V_2(t, x_e, y_e) \leq e^{-2\mu^*(\gamma)(t-t_0)} V_2(t_0, x_e(t_0), y_e(t_0)).$$

Therefore,

$$\sqrt{x_e^2(t) + y_e^2(t)} \leq e^{-\mu^*(\gamma)(t-t_0)} \sqrt{x_e^2(t_0) + y_e^2(t_0)},$$

for all $t > t_0$, $\sqrt{x_e^2(t_0) + y_e^2(t_0)} < \gamma$ and any γ . Furthermore, it can be concluded that the equilibrium point $(x_e, y_e) = (0, 0)$ is USGES ([33], Definition 2.7). ■

Remark 5: The convergence speed factor $\mu^*(\gamma)$ depends on several parameters. Clearly, the convergence rate will be higher for larger U and smaller Δ . Similarly, the convergence rate decreases with an increase in $|y_e(0)|$, $|x_e(0)|$ and $\hat{\beta}_{\max}$. It is worth noting that when initialized to zero, $\hat{\beta}(t)$ satisfies the inequality $|\hat{\beta}(t)| < \left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_0}{\sigma}}\right) |\beta|$, according to Remark 3.

C. STABILITY OF CASCADE SYSTEM

The estimation and guidance subsystems can be viewed as a cascade system. Let \mathcal{S}_2 denote the estimation subsystem that excites the guidance subsystem \mathcal{S}_1 , as shown in Fig. 2:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_1 : \begin{cases} \dot{x}_e = -k_1 x_e + \dot{\alpha}_d y_e + U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta}, \\ \dot{y}_e = -k_2 y_e - \dot{\alpha}_d x_e - U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)\tilde{\beta}, \end{cases} \\ \mathcal{S}_2 : \begin{cases} \dot{\tilde{z}} = (A(t) - [p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda\Lambda^T + P_z^{-1}]\Sigma)\tilde{z} + \Phi(t)\tilde{\beta}, \\ \dot{\tilde{\beta}} = -p_\beta^{-1}\Lambda^T\Sigma\tilde{z}. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

In the following we prove the stability of the cascade system.

Theorem 1: The AO-LOS guidance law given by (14) and (16) together with the adaptive observer (7)-(8), renders the origin of the cascade system (23) USGES.

Proof: Lemma 1 establishes that the subsystem \mathcal{S}_2 is UGES, while Lemma 2 demonstrates that the subsystem \mathcal{S}_1 with $\tilde{\beta} = 0$ is USGES. Furthermore, the interconnection function $g(t, x_e, y_e) = [U \sin(\psi - \alpha_d), -U \cos(\psi - \alpha_d)]^T$ satisfies $\|g(t, x_e, y_e)\| = U$. Therefore, the cascade system $\mathcal{S}_1 - \mathcal{S}_2$ fulfills the conditions of Proposition 2.3 by Loría et al. [33], which ensures that its origin is USGES. ■

Remark 6: The proposed sideslip estimation subsystem is shown to be UGES, while the equilibrium point of the cascade system is proven to be USGES. On the other hand, the PLOS-based guidance system [25] is UGAS, which represents a weaker stability property. As a result, the proposed method provides faster convergence speed and more robust path following performance across various USV velocities than the PLOS method. Furthermore, the ELOS [22] is proven to be ISS-stable and can also provide fast estimation of the sideslip angle. However, it relies on a reduced-order observer

to estimate the sideslip angle, making it more sensitive to measurement noise than the proposed estimator.

IV. SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, the simulation and experimental results are presented to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed guidance law.

A. SIMULATION RESULTS

The AO-LOS is compared with the ELOS [22] and PLOS [25] guidance laws in two examples involving straight-line and curved path following. The algorithm parameters are chosen to achieve a trade-off between convergence speed and sensitivity to measurement noise. Specifically, the parameters of the proposed algorithm are $\Delta = 5$ m, $k = 10$, $\rho_z = 1.3$, $\rho_\beta = 1.6$, $\Sigma = 1.6I_2$. In the PLOS algorithm, the following parameters are selected: $\Delta = 5$ m, $k = 10$, $k_1 = 3$, $k_2 = 3$ and $\alpha = 0.2$, while in the ELOS $\Delta = 5$ m, $k = 0.1$ and $\kappa = 10$ are used. Additionally, in the third example, the influence of the AO-LOS parameters on estimation performance is examined.

The yaw dynamics of the USV is modeled as in [16]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\psi} = r, \\ \tau \dot{r} + r = a\delta, \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

where ψ , r and δ denote the yaw angle, yaw rate and the rudder angle. The rudder angle is generated by a PD controller and is defined as $\delta(t) = K_p(\psi - \psi_d) + K_d\dot{\psi}$. The parameters of the USV and the control law are set as follows: $a = 20$, $\tau = 1$, $K_p = 0.6$, and $K_d = 0.35$.

1) Straight-line path following

In the first example, we consider a straight-line path following problem. The path-tangential angle is set to $\alpha_d = 13^\circ$. The initial position of USV is chosen as $[x_0 \ y_0]^T = [0 \ 5]^T$, while the initial heading angle is $\psi_0 = 0^\circ$. The surge velocity is $u = 3$ m/s, whereas the sway velocity is $v = 0.3$ m/s, which results in the sideslip angle $\beta = 5.71^\circ$.

The estimated sideslip angle, USV trajectory, and cross-track error under different LOS algorithms are shown in Figs. 3a, 3b and 3c. It can be seen that all estimators accurately estimate the sideslip angle, with the AO-LOS algorithm exhibiting the fastest convergence speed. As a result, the AO-LOS algorithm also achieves the fastest convergence to the desired path. The actual and desired heading angles produced by considered guidance systems are depicted in Fig. 3d.

To assess the robustness of the considered algorithms to initial conditions, three additional scenarios are examined. In the first scenario, the velocities u and v are varied, while in the second and third scenarios, different values of the initial position and orientation are considered. Other parameters, including the algorithms' settings, remain unchanged. Fig. 4a shows the estimated sideslip angle for different surge velocities: $u = 3$ m/s, $u = 6$ m/s, $u = 1.5$ m/s. It should be noted that the sway velocity is proportionally adjusted to keep

(a) Estimated sideslip angle

(b) Path following performance

(c) Cross-track error

(d) Actual and desired heading angle

FIGURE 3. Performance comparison of different LOS guidance laws during straight-line path following.

(a) Comparison for different surge velocities

(b) Comparison for different initial positions

(c) Comparison for different initial heading angles

FIGURE 4. Performance comparison of different sideslip estimators during straight path following.

the sideslip angle unchanged. It can be observed that the AO-LOS and ELOS exhibit consistent convergence speed across all three cases, whereas the estimation performance of the PLOS algorithm significantly depends on the surge velocity. Fig. 4b illustrates the estimated sideslip angle for three different initial positions. It can be observed that the AO-LOS and PLOS exhibit consistent performance across all three scenarios, while the ELOS performance depends on the initial position. Furthermore, in Fig. 4c, it is evident that the initial orientation slightly affects the performance of the ELOS and

FIGURE 5. Performance comparison of different sideslip estimators during curved path following.

PLOS, whereas the AO-LOS performance remains the same for all three initial orientations of the USV. Finally, it can be concluded that the proposed sideslip estimator exhibits the strongest convergence and robustness properties, attributed to the UGES stability property of its equilibrium point.

2) Curved path and time-varying sideslip angle

In the second example, we consider a curved path following problem. The parameterized path is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x_d &= \theta, \\ y_d &= 50 \cos(0.1\theta). \end{aligned}$$

The USV is exposed to an irrotational ocean current with magnitude V_c and direction β_c , causing a time-varying sideslip angle. In this scenario, the surge and sway velocities in absolute coordinates are given by $u = u_r + u_f$ and $v = v_r + v_f$, where u_r and v_r represent the USV velocity components relative to the water. Furthermore, $v_f = V_c \cos(\beta_c - \psi)$ and $u_f = V_c \sin(\beta_c - \psi)$ denote the velocity components induced by the ocean current [16]. Specifically, during the first 50 seconds, $V_c = 0.3$ m/s and $\beta_c = 30^\circ$, while for the rest of the simulation, $V_c = 0.4$ m/s and $\beta_c = 20^\circ$. Additionally, the position and velocity measurements are corrupted by white Gaussian noise with a variance of 0.01.

Fig. 5 shows the estimated sideslip angle for $v_r = 0$ and different relative surge velocities: $u_r = 3$ m/s, $u_r = 4$ m/s, and $u_r = 2$ m/s. It can be seen that the AO-LOS algorithm converges the fastest in all three cases. Furthermore, the convergence speed of the AO-LOS and ELOS is unaffected by surge velocity, while the estimation performance of the PLOS algorithm significantly depends on the surge velocity.

FIGURE 6. Curved path following under different LOS methods.

FIGURE 7. Comparison of the cross-track errors of different LOS methods during curved path following.

On the other hand, the ELOS algorithm is the most sensitive to measurement noise. It should be noted that the convergence speed of all estimators can be increased by adjusting the algorithm parameters, albeit at the cost of increased sensitivity to noise. The USV trajectories and cross-track errors are shown in Figs. 6 and 7, demonstrating that the AO-LOS outperforms the other algorithms.

FIGURE 8. Performance of the proposed sideslip estimator for different values of Σ , ρ_z and ρ_β .

3) Influence of the AO-LOS parameters

In this example, we analyze the influence of different parameters of the adaptive Kalman-like observer on estimation performance. The reference path and the irrotational ocean current are defined as in the previous example, resulting in a time-varying sideslip angle. The USV surge and sway velocities relative to water are set to $u_f = 4$ m/s and $v_f = 0$ m/s. In the first scenario, Σ is varied, while ρ_z and ρ_β are kept at the same values as in the previous example. Similarly, in the second and third scenarios, ρ_z and ρ_β are varied, while keeping the remaining parameters unchanged.

From Fig. 8, it can be seen that Σ mainly affects the performance during the transient process, while the tracking speed is not affected by this parameter. Specifically, for smaller Σ , the estimated sideslip angle converges faster to the actual value. However, it is worth noting that the use of large values of Σ may result in overshoot, particularly when sudden changes in the sideslip angle occur. On the other hand, increasing ρ_z enhances the algorithm's tracking speed but also increases sensitivity to measurement noise, while too small values of ρ_z can cause overshoot. Additionally, the tracking performance can be improved by increasing ρ_β . However, sensitivity to noise also increases with this parameter. It should be noted that the obtained results are in accordance with (12). Finally, it can be concluded that algorithm parameters should be carefully chosen to achieve a trade-off among different performance requirements.

B. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The AO-LOS guidance law was implemented on an omnidirectional marine surface vehicle described in [35], and ex-

FIGURE 9. Results of the first experiment: actual and reference trajectories of the USV.

FIGURE 10. Results of the first experiment: a) cross-track error, b) estimated sideslip angle, c) desired and actual heading angle.

periments were conducted on Jarun Lake in Zagreb, Croatia. The AO-LOS parameters were set to: $\Delta = 1$ m, $k = 0.5$, $\rho_z = 0.12$, $\rho_\beta = 0.12$, and $\Sigma = 0.1I_2$. PD and PI controllers were employed to control the heading angle and surge speed, respectively, while the sway speed was set to zero to simulate an underactuated vehicle. The USV's position was measured relative to an RTK base station located on the lake's shore.

1) Straight-line path following

In the first experiment, a straight-line path following problem was considered. The path-tangential angle was set to $\alpha_d = 30^\circ$, and the USV surge velocity was set to 0.3 m/s. Fig. 9 illustrates the actual and reference trajectories of the USV, whereas Fig. 10 shows the cross-track error, the estimated sideslip angle, and both the actual and reference heading angles. It can be seen that the USV converges to the desired straight line, with the cross-track error remaining within ± 0.04 m in the steady state. Furthermore, the estimated sideslip angle varies over time and even reaches -12° due to the low USV surge velocity. Despite this, the USV effectively maintains the desired straight path.

FIGURE 11. Results of the second experiment: actual and reference trajectories of the USV.

FIGURE 12. Results of the second experiment: a) cross-track error, b) estimated sideslip angle, c) desired and actual heading angle.

2) Curved path following

In the second experiment, a curved path following scenario was investigated. The reference path was defined as

$$\begin{aligned} x_d &= -45 + 10 \sin \theta, \\ y_d &= 43 + 10 \cos \theta, \end{aligned}$$

which corresponds to a circle with a radius of 10 and a center at $\{-45, 43\}$. For this experiment, the USV surge velocity was set to 0.4 m/s. The actual and reference trajectories of the USV are shown in Fig. 11, while the cross-track error, estimated sideslip angle, actual and reference heading angles are shown in Fig. 12. It can be observed that the USV closely follows the desired path. Although there are two small peaks in the cross-track error during the first lap, the error remains consistently below 0.11 m during the second lap. Furthermore, due to the curved path, the sideslip angle oscillates but

with a smaller magnitude compared to the first experiment, as the USV surge speed is higher in this case.

V. CONCLUSION

An adaptive observer-based LOS guidance law for path following of USVs in the presence of environmental disturbances has been proposed in this paper. In the proposed approach, the sideslip angle is treated as an unknown system state and is estimated along with the along-track and cross-track errors using an adaptive Kalman-like observer. It has been proven that the proposed sideslip estimator is UGES, while the origin of the cascade system composed of the sideslip estimator and guidance law is USGES. Simulation results indicate that the AO-LOS method provides faster convergence speed and smaller tracking error compared to other LOS methods. Additionally, the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm has been validated through experiments on a real vehicle, confirming its practical applicability.

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